

yellowing, blast (Bl), and bacterial blight (BB), and resistant to grain discoloration in farmers' fields. Under artificial inoculation, it was moderately resistant to RTV and Bl. In 1984, when

all other medium-duration varieties succumbed to an epidemic outbreak of leaf yellowing, Improved White Ponni tolerated the stress throughout Tamil Nadu. It is moderately resistant to mite

and green leafhopper (GLH), the vector for transmitting RTV (Table 2).

Cooking quality is very good, protein content is 9.88%. *S*

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

No first internode found in Nepalese varieties

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Four groups of Nepalese local cultivars were measured for internode elongation at maturity. Group 1 consisted of 15 local rice varieties that are tall, photoperiod insensitive, and mature within 110 d. Group 2 consisted of seven Gamadi-type local varieties in which the panicle does not exert from heading to maturity but remains enclosed in the flag leaf sheath. Other names for the Gamadi-type are Garvey, Dulhaniya, Kaniya, Thagiya, Sathi, and Satha. These varieties are dwarf type and mature within 100 d. Group 3 consisted of 36 local upland rice cultivars that are tall and mature in 100-110 d. Group 4 consisted of 20 local cultivars that are tall and photoperiod sensitive.

Direct seeding of groups 1, 2, and 3 was on 7 Apr and of group 4 on 15 Jun 1985 in the main plot under normal cultural conditions. Ten main culms were randomly sampled from 10 plants of each variety and culm length, panicle length, and length of each elongated upper internode measured.

All groups except group 2 showed normal elongation of the upper internodes, although total culm length varied significantly (see figure). In group 2, the first internode from the top was absent but the rest of the upper internodes showed normal elongation. This absence of the first internode from the top coincided with panicle enclosure within the flag leaf sheath and is important in the evolution of rice from the wild stage to cultivation. *S*

Internode elongation of Nepalese local germplasm.

Screening for dormancy in 39 rice varieties

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The 39 varieties screened had these maturity characteristics: 2 early maturing aus, photoperiod insensitive, 90-100 d maturity; 16 early maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, 140-148 d; 12 medium maturing aman,

photoperiod sensitive, 160-165 d, and 9 medium-late and late maturing aman, photoperiod sensitive, more than 165 d.

Seeds for three replications were thoroughly dried in the sun, cleaned, and kept in the laboratory in thin cloth bags at room temperature. Germination tests were started 10 d after harvest at regular intervals until dormancy was completely broken.

Seeds were germinated in petri dishes on moist blotting paper for 6 d. When

necessary, they were incubated at 30° C to avoid adverse effects of atmospheric low temperatures.

The varieties were classified by dormancy (time to 80% germination) as follows: nondormant, seed dormancy broken 10 d after harvest (DH); weakly dormant, dormancy broken 40 DH; moderately dormant, dormancy broken 60 DH; and strongly dormant, more than 60 d to break dormancy.

Long dormancy (80 to 100 d) was found more in medium and late maturing varieties (see table).

Exceptions were the early maturing Dular with moderate dormancy (60 d) and very late maturing Baok with no dormancy. *ff*

Dormancy in 39 rice varieties, Hooghly, West Bengal, India.

Maturity group	Nondormant (10 d)	Weak dormancy (40 d)	Moderate dormancy (60 d)	Strong dormancy (80-100 d)
Early aus	Satika	—	Dular	—
Early aman	CR205	EMH3 CR201 AC517 Dudhkati CR205	Badkalamkati 65 Churnakati Malsira Jhulur Asuda Badkalamkati T-1	Dudhraj KXI-36 Sankarkalma
Medium aman	—	Rupsail	Bhasamanik Kalma 222 Dudhsar Nagra Indrasail	Latisail Patnai 23 Jhingasail SR26B Radhunipagal Badsabhog
Medium-late and late aman	Baok	NC1281	Gabura OC1393	NC678 Kumargore Tilakkachari Achra FR43B

Effect of gamma-radiation on germination and seedling growth

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Four rice varieties — Sonalee, Prasad, IR36, and Tetep — and the F₂ of Sonalee/Prasad, Sonalee/IR36, and Sonalee/Tetep were irradiated with 30 and 40 krad gamma rays from ⁶⁰Co source and germinated in the incubator at 37° C.

Germination and root shoot length were measured at 10 d. All treatments reduced germination (see table). Lowest germination was shown by Sonalee at 30 krad (63%) and 40 krad (59%). IR36 exhibited maximum germination. Germination in Sonalee/Prasad was higher than that of either parent but was less in Sonalee/IR36 and Sonalee/Tetep.

Root and shoot length decreased as irradiation increased in all populations; the lowest values were for Tetep with 40 krad. Radiation affected roots more than it did shoots.

The hybrid Sonalee/Prasad had shorter roots than either parent; the

Effect of radiation on germination and seedling growth, Karnal, India.

Genotype	Germination (%)	Root length (mm)	Shoot length (mm)
<i>No radiation</i>			
Sonalee	81	13.60	7.10
Prasad	90	14.27	12.30
Sonalee/Prasad	100	12.64	11.09
IR36	95	15.89	11.24
Sonalee/IR36	81	15.45	13.77
Tetep	100	14.46	12.10
Sonalee/Tetep	81	16.85	14.83
<i>30 krad</i>			
Sonalee	63	4.67	9.81
Prasad	85	4.34	8.00
Sonalee/Prasad	90	8.23	9.20
IR36	90	10.93	11.46
Sonalee/IR36	72	9.88	11.12
Tetep	72	7.92	10.92
Sonalee/Tetep	72	9.77	8.37
<i>40 krad</i>			
Sonalee	59	1.95	4.94
Prasad	72	3.24	6.26
Sonalee/Prasad	85	2.57	5.59
IR36	85	3.62	5.31
Sonalee/IR36	70	6.95	7.21
Tetep	81	1.31	1.86
Sonalee/Tetep	70	3.86	4.87

hybrid Sonalee/Tetep had longer roots than either parent. In Sonalee/IR36, root length was intermediate.

Shoots of Sonalee/IR36 and

Sonalee/Tetep populations were longer than those of the parent varieties; in Sonalee/Prasad, shoot length was intermediate. *ff*